

Kinetics of Oxidation of Cyclic Alcohols by Acid Bromate

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Manuscript received 11 October 1977, revised 4 March 1978, accepted 26 April 1978

The oxidation of cyclic alcohols with common rings (five, six and seven membered) by bromate has been studied in binary solvent mixture of acetic acid and water in the presence of sulphuric acid. The reaction is first order each in the substrate and the oxidant, and second order with respect to sulphuric acid. The rate of the reaction increases with increase in sulphuric acid concentration. The reaction was found to follow free radical mechanism. The order of the reactivity of the alcohols is cyclopentanol < cyclohexanol < cycloheptanol, which is in conformity with Bayer strain theory. Increasing the acetic acid content of the medium the rate increases, and the reaction has been described as an ion-dipole reaction.

THE oxidation of cyclic alcohols have been studied with different oxidants like Vanadium(V)¹, Ce(IV)² and Cr(VI)³ in acid medium and with hexacyanoferrate(III)⁴ in basic medium. But no work seems to have been done on oxidation of cyclic alcohols with bromate ion. Though potassium bromate is a powerful oxidising agent with oxidation potential 1.4 volts in acid medium, it was used as a source of Br₂ in presence of Br⁻ ion. In the present study of bromate oxidations, the product Br⁻ ion formed in the reaction mixture reacts with Br(v) to generate bromine which on accumulation oxidises the substrate along with bromate ion. Hence to eliminate bromine oxidation, which is much faster than the oxidation by bromate ion, the product bromide ion has been suitably complexed as soon as it is formed, by use of mercuric acetate.

In continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation of phenols by bromate⁵ we are communicating in this report the results of pure bromate oxidation of cyclic alcohols with common rings (five, six and seven membered) at various temperatures in the range 40-60° and in various amounts of acetic acid as solvent. The experimental details are given in our earlier paper⁵.

Results and Discussion

The order of reactivity for the cyclanols (Table 1)

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF SULPHURIC ACID ON THE RATE OF REACTION

(BrO₃⁻) = 5 × 10⁻³ M; (cyclanol) = 5 × 10⁻² M;
[Hg(CH₃COO)₂] = 0.01 M

Acetic acid = 40%; Temperature = 30°

$k \times 10^3 \text{ l m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$

(H ₂ SO ₄)/M	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0
Cyclopentanol	0.58	1.62	3.21	5.13	8.56
Cyclohexanol	0.75	2.32	5.12	10.2	12.6
Cycloheptanol	0.64	2.70	6.08	12.1	20.5

is cyclopentanol < cyclohexanol < cycloheptanol which is in ascending order of ring size, is in conformity with Bayer strain theory but not with I strain hypothesis. This order is different from the orders found in V(V), Ce(IV) and Cr(IV), where the interpretation was suggested on the basis of I strain hypothesis. This ascending order of ring size was also found in the oxidation of alcohols by hexacyanoferrate(III) in basic medium⁴.

The reactivity of cyclohexanol can be explained by assuming that it is reacting through its flexible boat form rather than the chair form, because chair form is more stable. In the boat form there is no angle strain but there is bond opposition strain, involving four pairs of hydrogens at the side of the boat and also the strain due to the pair of hydrogens at the top of the boat known as the bowspritflagpole interaction⁶. As a result of these interactions the boat form is less stable than the chair form.

The reaction is first order in oxidant and substrate and second order with respect to sulphuric acid. The rate was found to be increased on increasing sulphuric acid studied in the range 0.1M to 1.0M and it was observed log *k* against pH was linear with slopes of 1.8 to 2.0. The reactions were studied with different percentages of acetic acid, (Table 2) and plot of log *k* against 1/D was linear

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACETIC ACID ON THE RATE OF REACTION

(BrO₃⁻) = 5 × 10⁻³ M; (Cyclanol) = 5 × 10⁻² M;
[Hg(CH₃COO)₂] = 0.01 M

(H₂SO₄) = 0.4 M; Temperature = 30°

$k \times 10^3 \text{ l m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$

% Acetic acid	10	20	30	40	50
Cyclopentanol	0.33	0.46	0.83	1.62	4.05
Cyclohexanol	0.42	0.74	1.28	2.32	6.39
Cycloheptanol	0.53	0.90	1.42	2.70	7.33

with a positive slope indicating that the reaction is between a cation and a dipole. The cation should be the protonated bromate ion $H_2BrO_3^+$ which is in consistence with order being two with respect to hydrogen ions.

The reaction was studied at different concentration of substrate (Table 3). The slopes of

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CYCLANOL ON THE RATE OF REACTION

$(BrO_3^-) = 5 \times 10^{-3} M$; $(H_2SO_4) = 0.4 M$; Acetic acid = 40%
 $[Hg(CH_3COO)_2] = 0.01 M$; Temperature = 90°
 $k \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$

(Cyclanol)/M	0.05	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25
Cyclopentanol	4.85	9.50	13.20	17.06	23.03
Cyclohexanol	6.95	14.00	19.19	25.60	31.62
Cycloheptanol	8.10	15.38	20.51	26.71	33.77

$\log k_{obs}$ vs. \log (cyclanol) were not strictly unity. The data also yield linear plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs. $1/(\text{cyclanol})$ with definite intercept indicating the formation of cyclanol-bromate complex and also suggesting that rate expression is of the form,

$$\frac{-d[Br(V)]}{dt} = Kk [ROH] [Br(v)] / 1 + Kk [ROH]$$

where K is the equilibrium constant for the formation of alcohol-bromate complex and k is the disproportionation constant of the complex.

The oxidation was studied in the temperature range 40-60° and the activation energies for cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol and cycloheptanol were 18.3, 14.1 and 16.6 K cal respectively. The products of oxidation were found to be corresponding cyclic ketones and bromide ion. The ketones were identified by comparing the m.p. of their 2,4-DNP derivatives with the authentic samples. The formation of Br^- ion was confirmed by the addition of $AgNO_3$ to the reaction mixture. Free radicals were detected in the system by the addition of acrylonitrile and acrylamide.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (V.L.) wishes to thank C.S.I.R. (New Delhi) for award of J.R.F.

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